

Assessment of Perception and Attitude on English Studies Curriculum among Junior Secondary School Teachers in Ibadan South-West Local Government, Oyo State

Ajagbe, Iyabode Mofoluwake¹

Email: folukehinmowo@gmail.com

Tel: 08059396073

Olatunji, Sheriff Olamide²

Email: olatunjisheriff07@gmail.com

Tel: 07034593781

¹Department of Arts and Social Sciences Education, University of Ibadan

²Department of Arts and Social Sciences Education, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja

Abstract

The study investigated assessment of perception and attitude on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school teachers in Ibadan South-West Local Government, Oyo State. The study adopted the survey research design. Population of the study consists of all junior secondary school teachers in public junior secondary schools in Ibadan South-West Local Government Area, Oyo State during the 2021/2022 academic session. Forty (17 Male and 23 Female) teachers constitute the sample size of the study. The sample size was selected using multi-stage sampling technique. Two research instruments were used for data collection: Teachers' Perception of English Studies Curriculum Questionnaire ($r=.76$) and Questionnaire on Teachers' Attitude to English Studies Curriculum ($r=.80$). Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of percentage, mean, standard deviation and inferential statistics of t-test. Findings of the study that there was a weighted mean of 2.84, which is greater than the threshold set at 2.50 and a weighted mean of 1.77, which is lower than the threshold set at 2.50. Also, there was a significant difference in the mean response scores of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school male and female teachers. So, the null hypothesis was accepted. There was no significant difference in the mean response scores of attitudes on English Studies Curriculum among Junior Secondary School male and female teachers. So, the null hypothesis was rejected. It could be concluded that the study has provided a better understanding of perception and attitude on English Studies curriculum among Junior Secondary School teachers in Ibadan South-West Local Government, Oyo State. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that government should do everything possible to educate teachers of English Studies on reasons for English Studies Curriculum at Junior Secondary School level.

Keywords: Teacher's perception, attitude, English Studies, curriculum

Introduction

The objectives of the English studies curriculum are to broaden the language competencies students have developed through Basic Education, so that they are able to use English with increasing level of proficiency for personal and intellectual development, effective social interaction, further study, vocational training, work and pleasure. To enable learners further develop their interest and confidence in using English as their understanding and mastery of the English language grows. To enable learners further broaden their knowledge, understanding and experience of various cultures in which English is used. After independence, English language was taught as a subject from primary school level through secondary to higher education. Literature in English was studied as a discipline and only introduced at senior secondary school level until the introduction of the 9-3-4 system of education which brought radical changes in the educational structure, the curriculum and in the teaching approach. Consequently, English language now become English Studies (Ajagbe, 2020).

The English Studies curriculum contents are harnessed to enable pupils learn, internalise and use what has been learnt for solving real life problems. While the primary school pupils are exposed only to English language skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing), the junior secondary school are exposed to English language and Literature genres (Saidu & Haruna, 2020). This is meant to expose the students to a wide range of English language and literary skills that should enhance their communicative skills. With this curriculum, it is believed that students will not only be competent users of English language but teaching and learning will be entertaining and interesting to them. For effective implementation of this curriculum, learners'

Assessment of Perception and Attitude ... (Ajagbe & Olatunji, 2023) DOI: <https://ddoi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10666893>

active participation during lessons through different activities, teaching styles and all-round assessment tools, have been suggested in the curriculum (Ajagbe, 2020).

Due to the importance attached to the English language in education, the Nigerian educational planners in Nigeria joined the two subjects into one for students to be exposed to a wide range of English language and literary skills that should enhance their communicative skills. The Junior Secondary School Curriculum states that English language is offered together with literature. Thus, in the National Curriculum for English language in the Junior Secondary School, the two subjects have been fused into one named “English Studies”. The integrated English teaching approach is part of the movement towards communicative language teaching (Lawal, 2019). Lambo, while commending the efforts behind the integrative English curriculum at the Junior Secondary School (JSS) level, stresses the need for effective implementation. Lambo suggests the need for periodic orientation or re-training of both teachers and supervisors in Junior Secondary Schools, in view of the fact that integrative teaching of English at the JSS level is innovative.

Magoma (2015) asserts that teachers of English felt that the content of English was too much and they felt burdened by the work they had to cover. Therefore, they advocated for the separation of English and literature. The implication is that the content to be covered dictates the methodologies to be used in teaching process. Sadeghi (2007) argues in favour of integration. Sadeghi states that literature should be a powerful tool in the hands of any teacher of English as a second or foreign language especially because language learning including literature is above all educational undertaking. Language and literature is interrelated entities, with teachers as users of literature rather than teachers of it. Secondary education syllabus states that through exposure to literature, the learner will improve their language skills. They will not only enrich their vocabulary but also learn to use language in variety of ways.

Despite the important nature of the revised English Studies curriculum which is to improve students’ reading ability and communicative competence, the performance of the junior secondary students is not satisfactory. Ajagbe (2020) maintains that the integration of the two subjects implies that the English language teachers in the JSS are now saddled with responsibility of teaching the new subject (English Studies), which consists of English language and Literature-in-English. Ajagbe asserts that the new arrangement is rocked with a number of problems. The teachers are faced with the problem of balancing the time allocation for the two aspects of the new subject at the junior secondary school level. Teachers at this level of education, do not normally give enough attention to the literature aspect of the subject in the class as many of them do not even know the rationale for merging the two subjects. As part of the problem affecting the implementation of English Studies curriculum is poor perception of teachers and poor attitude of teachers to the curriculum.

As a way of addressing causes of the problem, scholars have carried out studies on teacher factors and students’ learning outcomes in English Studies (Lawal, 2019), challenges and innovations in the teaching of English Studies (Ewetan and Ewetan, 2015) and teacher perception of curriculum objectives and learning experience as correlates of achievement in English Studies among junior secondary students in Ibadan, Nigeria (Adedigba and Fakeye, 2020). These studies came up with good contributions but with little emphasis on teacher’s perception of and attitude to English Studies Curriculum at junior secondary schools especially in Ibadan. The perception of teachers on English studies curriculum is very important for the purpose of engaging students in the best way and promotes quality teaching.

Williams (2016) views perception as a way to recognise and interpret information we gathered through our senses. This also includes how we respond to certain situations with the given information. Williams also asserts that besides the collection of information, perception involves active participation of higher cognitive functions responsible for constructing and interpreting ideas. Perception, as noted by Schacter, Gilbert and Wegner (2011), is the organisation, identification and interpretation of sensory information in order to represent and understand the environment. It is the way something is regarded, understood or interpreted. Romanov (2011) stated that perception includes senses, feelings, ideas, thought and theories. Therefore, perception is personally based on selection, organization and interpretation of the stimuli. Teachers’ perceptions have enormous effect on the successful implementation of quality education in schools, quality of teaching and quality of learning. Within any single subject areas, teachers’ perception will influence a range of teaching skills, styles, models and approaches that comprise a teaching repertoire and this will provide a clear framework for describing the teaching activities.

Attitude of English Studies teachers to English Studies curriculum depicts their positive or negative reaction towards the implementation of the curriculum. Attitude can be formed from an individual’s past or present and that it can be positive or negative evaluation of a people, objects, events, activities and idea about anything in the environment (Obiegbu, 2016). It is one’s feelings, thoughts and predisposition to believe in some particular manner towards some aspects of one’s environment. Attitude can be formed from an individual’s past or present and that it can be positive or negative evaluation of a people, objects, events, activities and idea about anything in the environment.

Assessment of Perception and Attitude ... (Ajagbe & Olatunji, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10666893>

English Studies curriculum at junior secondary schools comprises English language and Literature-in-English. It is also expected that with this merging, students' reading ability and communicative competence will improve and students will be empowered to use English language effectively after their completion of the Junior Secondary School. Despite the important nature of the revised English studies curriculum, the objectives of the curriculum are hardly met as evident in junior secondary school students' performance in English Studies. Studies have shown that the objectives of the curriculum were not met because of teachers' negative perception and negative attitude to English Studies curriculum. Efforts to address this problem have made researchers and scholars to investigate teacher factors and students' learning outcomes in English Studies, challenges and innovations in the teaching of English Studies and evaluation of junior secondary school English language curriculum. All these studies came up with good insights to the teaching and learning of English Studies at the junior secondary school level but with little emphasis on assessment of perception and attitude on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school teachers especially in Ibadan. Perception and attitude of teachers on English studies curriculum are very important for the purpose of engaging students in the best way and promotes quality teaching of English Studies. Therefore, this study investigated assessment of perception and attitude on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school teachers in Ibadan South-West Local Government, Oyo State.

Objectives of the Study

This study was carried to determine:

1. The mean response score of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State
2. The mean response score of attitudes on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State
3. The significant difference between mean response scores of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school male and female teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State
4. The significant difference between mean response scores of Attitudes on English Studies Curriculum among Junior Secondary School male and female Teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the mean response score of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among Junior Secondary School teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State?
2. What is the mean response score of attitudes on English Studies curriculum among Junior Secondary School teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between mean response scores of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among Junior Secondary School male and female teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State
2. There is no significant difference between mean response scores of Attitudes on English Studies Curriculum among Junior Secondary School male and female teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State?

Methodology

The study adopted the survey research design. Population of the study consists of all Junior Secondary School teachers in public Junior Secondary Schools in Ibadan South-West Local Government Area, Oyo State during the 2021/2022 academic session. Forty (17 Male and 23 Female) teachers constitute the sample size of the study. The sample size was selected using multi-stage sampling technique. Twenty (20) public junior secondary schools were randomly selected from 36 public secondary schools in Ibadan South West Local Government Area of Oyo State. Simple random sampling technique was used to select two English Studies teachers from each school making a total of 40 teachers (17 Male and 23 Female). Two research instruments were used for data collection. They are: Teachers' Perception of English Studies Curriculum Questionnaire ($r=.76$) and Questionnaire on Teachers' Attitude to English Studies Curriculum ($r=.80$). Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of percentage, mean, standard deviation and inferential statistics of t-test.

Results

Research Question 1

Assessment of Perception and Attitude ... (Ajagbe & Olatunji, 2023) DOI: <https://ddoi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10666893>

What is the mean response score of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State?

Table 1: The mean response score of perceptions on English Studies curriculum

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	StD
1	English Studies curriculum promotes learning of English language and literature	16 (41%)	10 (25.6%)	2 (5.1%)	11 (28.2%)	2.79	1.26
2	English Studies curriculum makes teachers to be hardworking	18 (46.2%)	10 (25.6%)	6 (15.4%)	5 (12.8%)	3.05	1.07
3	English studies curriculum makes teachers to have good attitude towards the teaching of literature	20 (51.3%)	5 (12.8%)	10 (25.6%)	4 (10.3%)	3.05	1.09
4	English Studies curriculum increases students' interest in English Studies	17 (43.6%)	12 (30.8%)	4 (10.3%)	6 (15.4%)	3.02	1.08
5	English Studies curriculum stimulates students' ability to think very fast.	18 (46.2%)	12 (30.8%)	3 (7.7%)	6 (15.4%)	3.07	1.08
6	English Studies curriculum is not objective	10 (27%)	6 (16.2%)	3 (8.1%)	18 (48.6%)	2.21	1.31
7	English Studies curriculum changes teachers' attitude towards teaching English	16 (41%)	5 (12.8%)	9 (23.1%)	9 (23.1%)	2.71	1.23
8	English Studies curriculum makes students learn new vocabularies from literary terms	24 (63.2%)	1 (2.6%)	6 (15.8%)	7 (18.4%)	3.10	1.24
9	Teaching English Studies curriculum can be a challenging activity	17 (44.7%)	8 (21.1%)	8 (21.1%)	5 (13.2%)	2.97	1.10
10	English studies curriculum facilitates the development of students' competence in writing	13 (33.3%)	12 (30.8%)	2 (5.1%)	12 (30.8%)	2.66	1.24
11	English studies curriculum does not develop students' speaking ability	18 (46.2%)	8 (20.5%)	4 (10.3%)	9 (23.1%)	2.89	1.23
12	Teaching English Studies curriculum makes students to be passive recipient of knowledge	23 (59%)	6 (15.4%)	1 (2.6%)	9 (23.1%)	3.10	1.25
13	Teaching contents of English Studies curriculum makes students to have positive attitude towards learning English.	17 (43.6%)	7 (17.9%)	8 (20.5%)	7 (17.9%)	2.87	1.17
14	English Studies curriculum changes teachers' wrong impression about teaching of English language	15 (38.5%)	3 (7.7%)	8 (20.5%)	13 (33.3%)	2.51	1.31
15	English studies curriculum makes students to reflect on what they learnt	14 (35.9%)	12 (30.8%)	8 (20.5%)	5 (12.5%)	2.89	1.04
16	Teaching contents of English Studies curriculum makes students attend English Studies classroom regularly	19 (50%)	1 (2.6%)	11 (28.9%)	7 (18.4%)	2.84	1.24
17	Teaching contents of English Studies curriculum makes students to enjoy reading literary texts	13 (33.3%)	4 (10.3%)	11 (28.2%)	11 (28.2%)	2.48	1.23
18	Contents of English studies curriculum are not easy to teach	17 (45.9%)	6 (16.2%)	3 (8.1%)	11 (29.7%)	2.78	1.31
19	English Studies curriculum fosters learning	21 (53.8%)	5 (12.8%)	6 (15.4%)	7 (17.9%)	3.02	1.20
20	Teaching contents of English Studies curriculum makes students to be eager to learn.	20 (54.1%)	2 (5.4%)	4 (10.8%)	11 (29.7%)	2.83	1.36
Weighted Mean = 2.84; Threshold = 2.50							

Data collected by the researchers (2021)

Assessment of Perception and Attitude ... (Ajagbe & Olatunji, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10666893>

Table 1 shows the perception of teachers about English Studies curriculum. The result indicates a weighted mean of 2.84, which is greater than the threshold set at 2.50. This implies that the selected teachers had a positive perception about the English studies curriculum. Out of the 20 items used, 11 items contributed to this positive perception because their means are greater than the weighted mean. The items are item 2 – English Studies curriculum is important for students’ performance in English Studies (mean = 3.05), item 3 – English Studies curriculum makes students to participate actively in English Studies instruction (mean = 3.05), item 4 – English Studies curriculum increases students’ interest in English Studies (mean = 3.02), item 5 – English Studies enables students’ to learn very fast (mean = 3.07), item 8 – English Studies curriculum makes students’ learn new vocabularies from literary terms (mean =3.10), item 9 – English Studies curriculum stimulates students’ ability to think very fast (mean =2.97), item 11 – English studies curriculum does not develop students’ speaking ability (mean = 2.89), item 12 – English studies curriculum makes students acquire a wide range of ideas about their work in English language (mean = 3.10), item 13 – English studies curriculum enable students to become more aware of their strengths (mean = 2.87), item 15 – English studies curriculum makes students to reflect (mean = 2.89), item 19 – The literature in English aspect of the English studies curriculum makes students perform poorly in the subject (mean =3.02). This implies that the selected teachers had a positive perception of the English studies curriculum.

Research Question 2

What is the mean response score of attitudes on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State?

Table 2: The mean response score of attitudes on English Studies curriculum

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std
1	I have poor attitude to the teaching of English Studies	1 (2.5%)	-	2 (5.0%)	37 (92.5%)	1.12	.515
2	I do not enjoy the teaching of English Studies curriculum	1 (2.5%)	-	8 (20.0%)	31 (77.5%)	1.25	.493
3	I teach English Studies curriculum with interest	1 (2.5%)	1 (2.5%)	26 (65.0%)	12 (30.0%)	1.77	.619
4	I am afraid to teach contents of English Studies curriculum	1 (2.5%)	-	20 (50.0%)	19 (47.5%)	1.57	.635
5	I am not encouraged to teach contents of English Studies curriculum	2 (5.1%)	3 (7.7%)	19 (48.7%)	15 (38.5%)	1.79	.800
6	I hate English Studies curriculum	-	2 (5%)	2 (30%)	26 (65%)	1.40	.590
7	I like teaching English Studies curriculum	1 (2.5%)	4 (10%)	14 (35%)	21 (52.5%)	1.62	.774
8	If I have my way, I will not teach the literature aspect of the curriculum	8 (20%)	7 (17.5%)	17 (42.5%)	8 (20%)	2.37	1.03
9	Teaching English Studies curriculum can be a boring activity	5 (12.5%)	7 (17.5%)	14 (35%)	14 (35%)	2.07	1.02
10	Teachers treat teaching of English Studies curriculum as an extra burden	1 (2.5%)	-	-	39 (97.5%)	1.07	.474
11	I am not comfortable teaching contents of English Studies curriculum	-	1 (2.5%)	13 (32.5%)	26 (65%)	1.37	.540
12	I always enjoy teaching the English aspect of the curriculum	7 (17.5%)	1 (2.5%)	18 (45%)	14 (35%)	2.02	1.04
13	I always enjoy teaching the Literature aspect of the curriculum	1 (2.5%)	3 (7.5%)	20 (50%)	16 (40%)	1.72	.715
14	Teaching contents of English Studies curriculum makes students to pay rapt attention in class	3 (7.5%)	1 (2.5%)	19 (47.5%)	17 (42.5%)	1.75	.839
15	I find English Studies curriculum too abstract to teach	2 (5%)	2 (5%)	9 (22.5%)	27 (67.5%)	1.47	.816
16	I have good impression about English Studies curriculum	5 (12.5%)	6 (15%)	11 (27.5%)	18 (45%)	1.95	1.06
17	I do not see good reason for merging the two subjects	4 (10%)	5 (12.5%)	15 (37.5%)	16 (40%)	1.92	.971

Assessment of Perception and Attitude ... (Ajagbe & Olatunji, 2023) DOI: <https://ddoi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10666893>

18	I teach English Studies curriculum for students to pass only.	3 (7.7%)	7 (17.9%)	18 (46.2%)	11 (27.5%)	2.05	.887
19	Teaching contents of English Studies curriculum is a waste of time	8 (20%)	3 (7.5%)	8 (20%)	21 (52.5%)	1.95	1.19
20	I see the teaching of English Studies curriculum to be challenging.	23 (57.5%)	7 (17.5%)	6 (15%)	4 (10%)	3.22	1.04
Weighted Mean = 1.77; Threshold = 2.50							

Data collected by the researchers (2021)

Table 2 shows the attitude of teachers to English Studies curriculum. The result indicates a weighted mean of 1.77, which is lower than the threshold set at 2.50. This implies that the selected teachers had negative attitude to the English studies curriculum. Out of the 20 items used, 10 items contributed to this negative attitude because their means are lower than the weighted mean. The items are item 1 – English studies curriculum makes teachers to have poor attitude to the teaching of English Studies (mean =1.12), item 2 – English Studies curriculum makes teachers to be hardworking (mean = 1.25), item 4 – English Studies curriculum changes teachers’ attitude towards teaching English (mean = 1.57), item 6 – I hate English Studies curriculum because it is difficult to teach to the students (mean = 1.40), item 7 – I don’t like English Studies curriculum because it is not useful in real life context (mean = 1.62), item 10 – Teachers treat teaching of English Studies curriculum as an extra burden (mean = 1.07), item 11 – Teachers do not teach the literature aspect of the English Studies curriculum (mean = 1.37), item 13 – Teaching English Studies curriculum makes students to be passive recipient of knowledge (mean = 1.72), item 14 – Teaching contents of English Studies curriculum makes students to pay rapt attention in class (mean = 1.75), item 15 – I find English Studies curriculum too abstract to teach (mean =1.47). In conclusion, the result implies that the selected teachers had poor attitude to English studies curriculum.

Testing the Null Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between mean response scores of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school male and female teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State

Table 3: Summary of t-test Analysis of the difference in mean response scores of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school male and female teachers

Variables			Std. Dev.	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remarks
	Mean	N			Lower	Upper				
Male	50.06	15	16.39	-10.14	-19.35	-.926	-2.23	37	.032	Sig.
Femal	60.20	24	11.97							

Data collected by the researchers (2021)

Table 3 shows the difference in the mean response scores of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school male and female teachers using the independent sample t-test analysis. The result indicates that there is a significant difference in the mean response scores of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school male and female teachers ($t_{(37)} = -2.23$; $p = .032 < .05$), with the female teachers (mean = 60.20) having a greater mean score than their male counterparts (mean = 50.06). So, the null hypothesis was accepted.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between mean response scores of Attitudes on English Studies Curriculum among Junior Secondary School male and female teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State?

Table 4: Summary of t-test Analysis of the difference in mean response scores of attitudes on English Studies Curriculum among Junior Secondary School male and female teachers

Variables			Std. Dev.	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remarks
	Mean	N			Lower	Upper				

Assessment of Perception and Attitude ... (Ajagbe & Olatunji, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10666893>

					Lower	Upper				
					r	r				
Male	35.53	15	5.85	.408	-2.93	3.74	.248	37	.806	Not Sig.
Female	35.12	24	4.41							

Data collected by the researchers (2021)

Table 4 shows the difference in the difference in mean response scores of Attitudes on English Studies Curriculum among Junior Secondary School male and female teachers using the independent sample t-test analysis. The result indicates that there is no significant difference in in mean response scores of attitudes on English Studies Curriculum among Junior Secondary School male and female teachers ($t_{(37)} = .248$; $p = .806 > .05$). So, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1 revealed that there was positive perception of teachers about English Studies Curriculum. The finding of this study is in line with Okunrila (2018) and Adegoke (2018) who found in their different studies that teachers had positive and good perception of the curriculum objectives of basic science and technology and French. The finding is contrary to Lawal (2019) who found that there was no significant relationship between teaching style and students' achievement in English Studies. Table 2 revealed that teachers had negative attitude to English Studies curriculum. This finding is in line with Waseka, Simatwa and Okwach (2016) who found that teacher's attitude has nothing to do with English Studies curriculum. This is contrary to the study of Adedigba and Fakeye (2020) who revealed that teachers' attitude and behaviour are very important to English Studies curriculum. Table 3 revealed that there was a significant difference in the mean response scores of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school male and female teachers. This finding is in line with Adegoke (2018) who found that there was a significant difference in the mean response scores of perceptions on French curriculum among junior secondary school male and female teachers. This is contrary to the finding of Lawal (2019) who found that there was a significant difference in the mean response scores of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school male and female teachers. Table 4 revealed that there was no significant difference in mean response scores of attitudes on English Studies Curriculum among Junior Secondary School male and female teachers. This finding is in line Waseka, Simatwa and Okwach (2016) who revealed that gender had no influence on teacher's attitude to curriculum implementation. This is against the finding of Lawal (2019) who revealed that gender had important influence on teacher's attitude influence to the implementation of the curriculum.

Conclusion

The study has shown that English Studies Curriculum could be enhanced by teacher's perception of and attitude to English Studies Curriculum. Based on the findings, this study has provided a better understanding of perception and attitude on English Studies curriculum among Junior Secondary School teachers in Ibadan South-West Local Government, Oyo State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that:

1. relevant educational bodies and stakeholders should ensure that teachers of English Studies have positive perception and attitude to English Studies Curriculum.
2. government should do everything possible to educate teachers of English Studies on the reasons for English Studies curriculum at Junior Secondary School level which comprises English language and Literature-in-English.
3. teachers should be involved in the design of English Studies curriculum for them to have positive perception and attitude towards it.
4. the Teaching Service Commission (TESCOM) and other educational bodies should organise seminars, workshops and other in-service trainings for English Studies teachers on importance of English Studies curriculum at the Junior Secondary School level.

Acknowledgements

We really appreciate all scholars and researchers whose works were cited in this study. We are grateful to all experts who did the face and content validity of the research instruments. All the research assistants are also appreciated for putting in their best.

Assessment of Perception and Attitude ... (Ajagbe & Olatunji, 2023) DOI: <https://ddoi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10666893>

References

- Adedigba, J.O & Fakeye, B. (2020). Teacher perception of curriculum objectives and learning experience as correlates of achievement in English Studies among junior secondary students in Ibadan, Nigeria. *International Journal of Arts and Social Sciences Education*. Vol. 5 No 2.
- Adegoke, A.O. (2018). Implementation of English Studies curriculum at senior secondary schools in Ondo, Nigeria, M.Ed. Project. Department of Teacher Education, University of Ibadan.
- Ajagbe I.M. (2020). Teacher's perception of and attitude to English studies curriculum at junior secondary schools in Ibadan South West Local Government Area, Nigeria. ASE 812 Presentation, Department of Arts and Social Sciences Education, University of Ibadan.
- Ewetan, T.O & Ewetan, O.O (2015). Teachers' teaching experiences and academic performance in Mathematics and English language in public secondary schools in Ogun State, Nigeria, *IJHSSE*, 2:2: 123-124.
- Saidu, D. & Haruna, A. S. (2020). Academic-related Stress among Language Lecturers in Federal College of Education, Kano: Counselling Intervention. *International Journal of Educational Realities-JERA* 10(1), 1-12. DOI: <https://doi.org.10.5281/zenodo.7264738>
- Lawal, A.E. (2019). Teacher factors and students' learning outcome in English Studies in Oluyole local government, Ibadan, Oyo State. *International Journal of Arts and Social Sciences Education*. Vol. 3 No 2.
- Magoma, C.M. (2015). Teacher related factors which influence the implementation of integrated English course in secondary schools: A case of Ibadan sub country, Kisii country: Unpublished M.Ed. Thesis. Kenyatta University.
- Obiegbo, I.R. (2016). Attitude of students/teachers to the use of information and communication technology in the teaching of English language in senior secondary schools in Awka, Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Research (IJAR)*1639-1649.
- Okunrinla, M.M. (2018). Classroom interaction and learning objectives as correlates of learning outcomes in basic science and technology in junior secondary schools in Akure, Nigeria. M.Ed. Project. Department of Arts and Social Sciences Education, University of Ibadan.
- Romanov, S.G. (2011). What is Perception? Retrieved March 31, 2019, from CrossFit Journal: [http://journal.crossfit.com/2011/06/romanov perception.tpl](http://journal.crossfit.com/2011/06/romanov%20perception.tpl)
- Sadeghi, K. (2007). The key for successful reader-writer interaction: Factors affecting reading comprehension in L2 revisited. *Asian EFL Journal*, 9(3), 198-200
- Schacter D.L, Gilbert D.T & Wegner D.M. (2011). *Psychology (2nd Edition)*. New York: Worth.
- Waseka, E.L., Simatwa, I.E. & Okwach, T.O. (2016). Influence of teacher factors on students' academic performance in secondary school education *Greener Journal of Education Research*, 4:5
- Williams, Y. (2016). What is Perception? Chapter 3.7 Williams' notes